

Generative AI as an Infrastructure Copilot: Automating Infrastructure-as-Code Across the DevSecOps Lifecycle

Online Appendix

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Abstract

Practitioners and researchers continuously focus on developing automation strategies to cope with the exponentially demanding need for the timely deployment of software projects in tight release schedules. Such automation techniques include Infrastructure-as-Code (IaC) and the DevOps and DevSecOps cycles. Recent studies investigated generative AI (GenAI) for generating infrastructure as code scripts. However, no studies have focused on using GenAI to generate scripts based on DevSecOps stage artifacts. Different IaC tools serve varied purposes, requiring specific infrastructure setups for different project stages. We envision GenAI models leveraging artifacts from each DevSecOps stage to create and refine IaC scripts. We trust our approach to have an impact on practitioners to leverage it as an automatic copilot for infrastructure design and deployment, and for researchers to build on our vision and future empirical validation.

Keywords: GenAI, IaC, DevOps, DevSecOps, Security, Agentic AI

Fig. 1 Envisioned GenAI enabled DSO architecture diagram.

1 Roadmap

This section presents a summary and overview of the future work concerning implementation and empirical validation of our vision as detailed in Section ???. Based on the described design, Figure 1 presents the envisioned DSO workflow diagram, which visually shows the introduction of the GenAI role component into the architecture. Moreover, the presented architecture depicts the IaC script creation and update in each of the workflow updates, as well as at a cross-stage after a complete DSO loop has been accomplished.

1.1 Implementation

To implement our vision, research efforts should investigate the state of the art of leveraging GenAI for generation of IaC scripts and other kinds of scripts through a systematic literature review or a mapping study, to understand the advantages and limitations of different available models and select the most suitable ones for each stage outlined in Section ???. Then, we should analyze and compare the efficiency of the existing/adopted GenAI models to human IaC scripts. More specifically, we shall test the implementation of different models for each stage of the DSO cycle. In Section ??, we presented the vision of which artifacts could be leveraged by GenAI models to create or refine the infrastructure, focusing on the development, testing, and deployment architectures. Implementing our approach should be translated into making a proof of concept, which would mainly focus on including hooks and triggers

at each stage that feed the current artifacts to the right GenAI model (see Figure 1), paving the way for the empirical validation. Such an implementation requires gathering data on projects leveraging IaC tools, while verifying the quality and compliance with standards and security practices of the respective IaC scripts.

1.2 Empirical Validation

The empirical validation of GenAI’s role in the DSO cycle must go through rigorous comparisons with human experts to establish reliability and effectiveness (see Figure 1). Our empirical validation aims to compare different GenAI-generated IaC scripts with state-of-the-art tools and human experts to understand whether they can be exploited as real tools or copilots, or if they fail at the current stage, therefore highlighting possible weaknesses, literature gaps, and future research directions.

To assess whether GenAI models can generate more efficient IaC scripts than human experts, we designed experiments along all the DSO stages. We hypothesize that GenAI models, powered by, for instance, RAG (Retrieval-augmented generation) and fine-tuning methods, can provide more efficient, secure, and adaptable IaC scripts than those created by humans, based on previous experience in other Software Engineering domains (Esposito and Palagiano 2024; Esposito et al. 2024).

In each stage, we will compare IaC scripts generated by GenAI models with those designed by experienced DSO engineers. We will focus on aspects such as correctness, adherence to best practices, security compliance, and responsiveness to changes. These experiments shall employ appropriate IaC platforms for each stage and choose the best GenAI models for handling the tasks, including state-of-the-art models. As a rule of thumb, we can not blindly trust a single model’s output. Therefore, this stage will leverage different GenAI models to compare and cross-validate outputs to strengthen our envisioned approach.

Moreover, we aim to employ and fine-tune RAG throughout the experiments to improve domain-specific knowledge and real-time data integration in GenAI. We will train the models on infrastructure configuration datasets and security best practices during fine-tuning (Esposito and Palagiano 2024). RAG models enable access to external knowledge bases and documentation during generation, making their outputs more accurate and contextually appropriate (Esposito et al. 2024).

In the **Planning** stage, we feed user stories, requirements, and architecture diagrams into GenAI models such as GPT-4 and OpenAI’s Codex, as well as Google’s PaLM and Microsoft’s Turing-NLG. We will explore whether fine-tuning the models or providing examples via RAG changes the models’ performance. We can target IaC tools such as Terraform and AWS CloudFormation because of their significant capabilities and industry-wide adoption (Ntentos et al. 2024). We will compare the generated scripts to those created by human engineers in terms of fitting the project requirements, scalability, and security guidelines.

During the **Development** stage, the GenAI models update the IaC scripts regarding changes made to the source code and configuration files. Those artifacts are processed by models allowing code understanding, such as OpenAI’s Codex DeepMind’s AlphaCode or Meta Llama. Models create the scripts based on Ansible and Chef, among others, showing the code changes and dependencies. The comparison has

been made regarding the accuracy of the updates and consideration of security issues, leveraging outputs from static analysis tools.

In the **Building** stage, we address the polyglotism challenge (Guerriero et al. 2019) by testing the proficiency of GenAI models to handle projects in multiple languages. We feed models with build scripts, dependency graphs, and Software Bills of Materials (SBOMs). We aim to generate IaC scripts for the building process; thus, we focus on containerization features and utilize platforms like Docker and Kubernetes. Resource utilization and efficiency of the scripts generated by GenAI and those from human experts are compared.

In the **Testing** stage, we feed test cases, expected test results, and evaluation metrics to GenAI models. The generated IaC scripts should be able to provision the required testing environments, leveraging environment setup utilities such as Vagrant and Puppet. The experiments for this stage should focus on how the generated scripts can satisfy testing needs and incorporate security mechanisms, especially concerning dynamic application security testing tool outputs.

In the **Releasing** and **Deploying** stages, GenAI models should optimize deployment scripts and ensure enforcement of secure releases. From release notes to deployment manifests to version control tags, GPT-4 and IBM’s Project Debater-type models can generate or refine IaC scripts to perform the deployment using platforms like Helm and Kubernetes. We can evaluate the scripts on metrics and indicators such as deployment success rate, security compliance to standards such as CIS Benchmarks, and the need for manual intervention.

During **Operating**, **Monitoring**, and **Responding**, models dynamically modify the IaC scripts by constantly analyzing real-time monitoring data, logs, and performance metrics. GenAI models can also further integrate monitoring tools such as Prometheus and recommend modifications in infrastructure toward improved performance and security. We will compare the effectiveness and speed of these models in making such adjustments against human operators, particularly in terms of response times to incidents and proactive ability.

Such an assessment aims to investigate whether Generative AI models can improve infrastructure management by automatically creating IaC scripts compared to traditional, human-driven approaches. It also seeks to evaluate how well these models perform against human experts, assessing their ability to produce secure, adaptable, and high-quality infrastructure configurations using a range of performance metrics.

2 Limitations and Ethical Implications

In this section, we acknowledge potential limitations and ethical implications of the proposed approach and discuss ways to mitigate them.

Complex Requirements. Currently, GenAI models can have difficulty understanding and accurately performing according to the most complex and risky project demands due to training data and contextual understanding limitations. We will mitigate this limitation by expanding GenAI training datasets with richer and more varied scenarios by adding continuous learning mechanisms where a human expert reviews and corrects GenAI output so that models can be fine-tuned over time.

Historical Data Quality. GenAI effectiveness hugely depends on the quality and quantity of the training data. Poor data may result in inaccurate or less-than-optimal IaC scripts (Siddiq et al. 2024). To mitigate this limitation, we will establish firm data governance practices that ensure constant collection and evaluation of relevant training data.

Security. IaC scripts, if automatically generated by GenAI, may introduce security vulnerabilities in case these are not properly validated (Mohsin et al. 2024; Zhang et al. 2025), or the dataset on which the model was trained was skewed or biased (Asare et al. 2023). This is inherited from IaC integration in DSO (Guerrero et al. 2019; Rahman 2018; Esposito et al. 2025). To mitigate this limitation, we must design security validation profiles, assess the consequences of specific infrastructure changes, and envision a human-in-the-loop for the most critical infrastructure changes, i.e., deletion of a service or cloud vendor migration.

Scalability. Scalability is highly challenging, especially for large and complex distributed infrastructure projects when integrating GenAI into all phases of the DSO cycle. To mitigate this limitation, we will focus on implementing modular GenAI components that can be incrementally integrated and scaled independently.

Explainability of AI. According to state-of-the-art research, AI-based models succeed in providing relevant outputs for software and risk assessment tasks (Esposito and Palagiano 2024). However, AI models rely on learning patterns from the data rather than acting based on algorithmic rules, and they cannot explain the reason for those specific outputs, thus becoming a *black-box* model type. GenAI is not an exception, and thus we must provide interpretability and explainability measures as part of the model (Esposito et al. 2024). To succeed in this, we will emphasize the introduction of explainable post-hoc metrics, such as kernel explainers (Ribeiro et al. 2016; Esteves et al. 2020) or permutation importance metrics (Breiman 2001; Amershi et al. 2019) in the different stages of DSO where GenAI is employed. This will allow the visualization of the parameters that influence the GenAI decision the most at each stage of the DSO cycle.

Ethical Implications According to Johnson and Menzies (2024), it is crucial to discuss ethical issues arising in all aspects of Software Engineering and not simply “look away.” Problems enabled by LLMs and Agentic AI include hallucinations, backdoor attacks, and privacy leakage (Zhang et al. (2025)). Zhang et al. (2025) discuss the differences between the concepts of safety, security, and privacy when considering risks of LLMs. Considering the ethical implications of leveraging GenAI during the software development process, De Souza et al. (2024) conducted a study on the potential impact of AI code generation tool on the software engineering job market. They extracted and analyzed 331 tweets with the highest engagement. The authors highlighted different sentiments in the narrative of how GenAI can shape the development life cycle, both in a positive way, as a learning tool and valuable assistant, and as a possibility of job theft. Similar to our previous study (Esposito et al. (2024)), this work envisions the adoption of GenAI as an infrastructure copilot. Nevertheless, human experts are needed both for domain knowledge and as supervisors for the most critical decisions. Therefore, we stress the

point that **GenAI should be** used as a **valuable assistant**, lifting the heavy work from experts, and **not as expert replacement**.

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